

SOME IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF ENGLISH ANECDOTES

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ANNOTATION

This article highlights some important aspects of anecdotes in spoken language. In addition, in what situations anecdotes are used, by whom they are told, and different tariffs are given in this article

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An anecdote is "a story with a point", such as to communicate an abstract idea about a person, place, or thing through the concrete details of a short narrative or to characterize by delineating a specific quirk or trait. Occasionally humorous, anecdotes differ from jokes because their primary purpose is not simply to provoke laughter but to reveal a truth more general than the brief tale itself. You probably know someone who has told a tale or two. These short personal stories are called anecdotes and can provide a lot of context about a time, place, or group. When writing an essay, you will undoubtedly touch upon a time period, a setting, or a culture for yourself. While an anecdote is one way to explore these topics, it should only be used if it's your best way to get the point across. Anecdotes themselves have a time and place! An anecdote is a story. It has a beginning, middle, and end, and has some kind of purpose. Like any story, an anecdote can be told well or told not-so-well. Writing and telling anecdotes

is an art form, like any form of storytelling. In writing an essay, paper, or article, anecdotes can be used in a number of ways. An anecdote uses descriptive imagery. This imagery often takes the form of rich sensory descriptions: auditory descriptions, gustatory descriptions, olfactory descriptions, tactile descriptions, and visual descriptions. An anecdote is personal. It is something that happened to you. It is usually about an event you experienced yourself, but it can also be about meeting someone who experienced an event. Either way, an anecdote draws upon something personal. Anecdotes cover a wide variety of stories and tales, especially since they can be about basically any subject under the sun. You might be checking out at the supermarket one day and the cashier comments on your brand of apple juice. Perhaps that will spark the employee to share a quick story about the summer she and her four-year-old went apple picking in Upstate New York. That's an anecdote; such stories come up all the time. Other everyday examples of anecdotes include:

I once had a border collie. She was so smart! Every morning, I'd open up the front door and she'd run out, pick up the newspaper and deliver it to my husband at the breakfast table.

Oh, I love Ireland! I visited the west coast six times last year. Last time I went to Kilmacduagh, an old monastery where the winds whip with songs of the deceased who are laid to rest there. While I was there, I swore I heard something. I think it was a ghost!

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